

Online Companion: Additional Material on the Practical Application and Empirical Evaluation of the Methodology in AIDOaRt

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1 Purpose of this Companion Document

This document reports the additional material supporting the experience report and the empirical evaluation presented in the main paper. It includes the figures and practical examples that illustrate how the methodology was instantiated in the European research project AIDOaRt [4] across its iteration path and three main phases. The material is intended to help readers understand the concrete traceability links among requirements, architecture components, technological solutions, and use-case scenarios. It also includes the detailed material supporting the empirical evaluation of the methodology: the considered quality framework and the detailed computation of the selected quality metrics, as well as the complete survey instrument, the background of its respondents, and the full analysis of the collected qualitative feedback.

The rest of this document is organized as follows. Section 2 provides an overview of the practical application of the methodology. Section 3 reports examples related to the Technology Plan step. Section 4 presents examples related to Technology Development and traceability at architectural-component level. Section 5 details an example of use-case development in the VCE scenario. Section 6 reports examples from the three main phases of the AIDOaRt architecture design process. Section 7 presents the quality framework considered for the evaluation and the rationale behind the selection of the measured metrics. Section 8 details the computation and interpretation of each measured quality metric. Section 9 reports the complete survey instrument. Section 10 describes the background of the survey respondents. Section 11 provides the full analysis of the qualitative feedback collected via the survey.

2 Overview of the Practical Application in AIDOaRt

Figure 1 provides an overview of the practical application of the proposed methodology in the context of AIDOaRt. It visually highlights the global evolution of the resulting architecture during the three years/phases of the project, corresponding to three consecutive instantiations of the iterative path. The figure shows how the process progressed from initial textual information collected in spreadsheets to a consolidated and refined architecture.

3 Technology Plan: Requirements, Use-Case Scenarios, and Roadmaps

During the Technology Plan step, the AIDOaRt framework requirements were elicited from industrial use-case requirements. In parallel, technological solution providers derived tool-component requirements for their tools, with the goal of satisfying use-case

requirements. Requirements for validating use-case datasets were also identified depending on specific scenarios.

All requirements were collected and structured by using a Model-Based Requirement Engineering approach. The objective was to support functional, non-functional, and data requirements, and to enable their reuse in the following steps of the architecture design process. Table 1 reports an excerpt of the requirements collected in AIDOaRt, including generic requirements and VCE-specific requirements.

Use-case scenarios and corresponding evaluation criteria were also defined during this step. The AIDOaRt use cases covered several industrial domains and addressed different kinds of systems, ranging from hardware-intensive developments to software-only scenarios. Table 2 shows an example of such a use-case scenario and related evaluation criteria in the context of the VCE use case.

At the end of the Technology Plan step, technological solutions were proposed by project partners to address the AIDOaRt use-case requirements according to the defined architecture. Some tools were then mapped to the generic requirements and considered as part of the architecture. Each partner also defined an initial roadmap for the development of its tools. Table 3 reports an example of an implementation roadmap for tool capabilities related to the VCE use case.

4 Technology Development: Architectural Components and Traceability

During Technology Development, the AIDOaRt architecture aggregated tool components specific to different application domains and applicable to one or several use cases. For each technological solution, the project collected offered services, functional descriptions, input and output data elements, technical constraints, access links, prototypes, and details about data requirements. This information was automatically imported into the designed architecture and then incrementally refined by partners.

Figure 2 reports three architecture components used in practice in the context of the VCE use case. The figure illustrates the Engagement & Analysis, AI for Modeling, and Model-Based Capabilities components, their corresponding tools, and potential relations to different use-case scenarios.

As shown in Figure 2, traceability links between use-case requirements and the main architectural components established indirect relations between tool components and use-case requirements. This provided a clear understanding of which use-case requirements could be satisfied during the project and which ones required additional external development.

Figure 1: Overview of the practical application of the proposed generic and iterative methodology for quality architecture design in the context of the AIDOaRT project.

Requirement name	Definition
GR_Mod_07	Use a model-based approach for ML representation
GR_Mod_09	Extend and customize standards modeling language to support aspect-oriented system development
VCE_R05	Customise standards based modelling frameworks, e.g., UAF, SysML, UML, and metamodels to develop system, software, and data architecture models
VCE_R07	Development of standard data classification, reusable definition, representation, and usage

Table 1: Excerpt of the AIDOaRt requirements, characterized by Generic Requirements (GR) for requirements engineering, modeling, coding, testing, or monitoring; Use Case Requirements (R); and Data Requirements (DR). This excerpt refers to the VCE use case.

VCE_UCS_01	
Name	Modeling system, software, data architectures
Actors	System architect, system engineer, software developer
Pre-conditions	Domain specific information items and system/software components
Post-conditions	Instances of architecture models
Evaluation criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ensures complete traceability across model elements from requirements to implementation. - Generates structured documentation, including architecture descriptions and traceability reports. - Supports OSLC-compliant import/export for seamless third-party tool integration. - Provides predefined templates to enhance tool interoperability and usability. - Aligns with MBPLE 26550 and ISO/IEC 42010 for compliance. - Supports domain-specific profiles and scales to CPSoS and services.

Table 2: Excerpt of the VCE use-case scenario and its evaluation criteria.

Tool – Capability	Description	In/Out parameters	Implem. level	Estim. delivery
AutomationML Modeling [14] – AML-Modeling	Textual and graphical modeling of AML artefacts with customizable validation routines.	Modeling/ AML models	Fulfilled	MS1(M6)
MER [9] – Modeling Process Mining	Catches modeling events from a Sirius-based graphical editor and generates an XES trace.	User modeling interactions in Sirius/XES log file	Partially implemented	MS5(M24)
EMF Views [5] – Model viewpoint and view specification	Specification of view(point) by defining the concerned elements from different (meta)models.	EMF (Meta)model/ Model view(point)	Partially implemented	MS4(M20)
MORGAN [10] – Recommender of model and metamodel elements	Specification of model and metamodel elements based on GNN.	(Meta)models dataset/ (Meta)model elements	Partially implemented	MS7(M32)

Table 3: Excerpt of the implementation roadmap for selected tool capabilities related to the VCE use case.

5 Use-Case Development: VCE Scenario

The AIDOaRt technological solutions were tested through use-case development. The corresponding activities involved integrating tools in the development processes of the use-case providers. Some tools were also developed with the objective of being used as project demonstrators.

Figure 3 shows the solutions developed for a VCE scenario and their links with several architecture components, including Model-Based Capabilities, Data Handling Capabilities, Engagement & Analysis, AI for Modeling, and Ingestion & Handling. It also shows how several generic and use-case requirements are related in this context.

This example shows how the traceability between components, requirements, and solutions was completed during use-case development. It also illustrates how the development of use cases allowed the specified technological solutions to be tested in practice, while the defined architecture components and related interfaces could be validated and refined accordingly.

6 Examples from the Three Main Phases

6.1 Initial Phase: Architecture Evolution

In the initial phase, the information needed to establish an initial version of the AIDOaRt architecture was collected. Descriptions of industrial use cases and technological solutions were analyzed and

(a) Engagement & Analysis component

(b) AI for Modeling component

(c) Model-Based Capabilities component

Figure 2: Three components of the AIDOaRt architecture used in practice in the context of the VCE use case, from the AI-Augmented Tool Set (a, b) and the Data and Modeling sub-component of the Core Tool Set (c), with their corresponding tools and potential relation to different use-case scenarios.

Figure 3: VCE use-case scenarios, derived requirements, provided solutions, specified functional interfaces, and instantiated architecture components.

prepared for integration within the architecture. As a result, a hierarchy of base components and sub-components was proposed, with each component offering or consuming services and capabilities.

Figure 4 reports an excerpt of the changes to the AIDOaRt architecture that occurred during the iterative stages. This example illustrates how architectural components and dependencies were refined as additional information from use cases and solution providers became available.

For instance, the Data Representation component was proposed to provide a common and global data representation serving as the foundation for model-based activities. This component relied on a megamodel unifying the different use-case data models [11]. Such a component could only be defined after collecting and analyzing information related to the use cases. Based on industrial feedback, dependency relationships between *Data Engineering* and *Core Engineering* components were considered. Another example concerned solution providers dealing with infrastructure, who pointed out the need for a component dedicated to *Computation Capabilities*. This component was intended to support tools automating the validation of infrastructure deployment and related tests [1].

6.2 Intermediate Phase: Integrated VCE and TEKNE Pipeline

In the intermediate phase, a more complete version of the AIDOaRt architecture was specified. It included enhanced descriptions of components, an extended list of functional interfaces and realizing solutions, development roadmaps, and integration links between solutions and case studies.

Figure 5 reports an excerpt from the VCE and TEKNE use-case implementation. It highlights components concerning the VCE use case, components concerning the TEKNE use case, and tools reused in both use cases.

In the VCE use case, a specific challenge concerned the definition and development of modeling patterns for VCE system architectures. The implementation relied on the tools reported in Table 3. As shown in Figure 5, the VCE implementation used *AutomationML* and the *CAEX Workbench* to define system models. To improve model usability, federated views were generated with *EMF Views* according to user needs. Then, the *MORGAN* recommendation tool was considered to assist engineers in modeling tasks. This tool uses process-mining techniques, supported by *MER*, to optimize and automate model recommendations.

This VCE example highlighted the need for additional interaction between several components of the proposed architecture. As a consequence, the dedicated functional interface *Modelling Process Tracing* was added to the *Model-Based Capabilities* architecture component.

6.3 Final Phase: Reuse and Validation in TEKNE

In the final phase, several updates were made to the designed architecture to accommodate consolidated technical and use-case requirements. These refinements relied on the full development of the underlying solutions and use cases.

The TEKNE use case focused on developing a cloud-enabled prognostic and health management system in the automotive domain. As shown in Figure 5, the *HEPSYCODE*¹ tool was integrated

¹HEPSYCODE Tool: <https://sites.mdu.se/aidoart/tools/tools/hepsycode>

Figure 4: Excerpt of the changes to the AIDOaRt architecture that occurred during the iterative stages.

Figure 5: Excerpt from the VCE and TEKNE use-case implementation. Orange components concern the VCE use case, yellow components concern the TEKNE use case, and blue components concern tools reused in both use cases.

for the development of the TEKNE² use case by reusing parts of the VCE implementation. TEKNE also integrated the modeling recommendation support already provided in the VCE use case by combining the MORGAN and MER tools. This provided a concrete validation of the AIDOaRt architecture with respect to the *Modelling Process Tracing* functional interface added during the intermediate phase.

²Tekne S.p.A.: <https://www.tekne.it/>

7 Empirical Evaluation: Quality Framework and Metric Selection

The main paper quantitatively evaluates the quality of the resulting AIDOaRt architecture based on one of the most recent MDE Software Architecture Quality frameworks³, as proposed in a comprehensive survey of the domain [18]. This work surveyed 33 selected papers from 2011 to 2022 and analyzed various existing approaches

³<https://tiziasan.github.io/QAandMetricsForArch/>

to assess the quality of software architectures. In this work, the authors identified a set of eight main *Quality Characteristics* that can be achieved by realizing one or more *Quality Attributes*. Each of these attributes can be measured with one or more *Quality Metrics*. In Figure 6, we represent in blue the specific metrics we evaluated in practice on the architecture resulting from the practical application of our methodology in the context of the AIDOaRt project. We represent in red the related quality attributes and in gray the corresponding main quality characteristics.

Figure 6: The architecture quality characteristics, attributes, and metrics considered for evaluating the application of the methodology in the context of AIDOaRt, based on the MDE SA Quality Framework [18].

The study distinguishes the metrics between “Generic” ones which generally apply to architectures in any domain, and “Specific” ones which are domain dependent (e.g., structural complexity or coupling measures that relate to automotive systems). It also distinguishes between “Internal” quality metrics which can be assessed based on the structure of the architecture model, and “External” which represent quality indicators that can only be perceived by the architecture users (e.g., completion of the realization or fulfillment of the requirements) or via the produced software artifacts (e.g., availability or response time).

In our case, we selected generic internal and external quality metrics. We opted for generic metrics, as the AIDOaRt architecture is meant to be domain independent. In particular, we considered three internal metrics, i.e., *Abstraction*, *Decomposition*, and *Understandability*, and two external metrics, i.e., *Decision Traceability* and *Requirement Fulfillment*. Importantly, all of these metrics are quantifiable in our context. We left the assessment of user-perceived external quality characteristics to the survey reported in the main paper and detailed in Sections 9 to 11. Note that we voluntarily skipped the 14 external quality metrics that require monitoring the running software framework to be produced based on the architecture. We also skipped Object-Oriented Programming (OOP)-specific metrics such as “Hierarchy”, “Inheritance”, and “Polymorphism” which are not particularly relevant in our case. We also avoided measuring more subjective quality metrics (e.g., Extensibility, Reponsibility, Suitability) that are defined as ratios of the number

of wisely designed architecture components (that are *believed* to be extensible, responsible, or suitable) over the total number of architecture components.

8 Empirical Evaluation: Detailed Metric Computations

This section details the computation and interpretation of each quality metric summarized in the main paper.

Abstraction quantifies a hierarchy level or degree of abstraction. It is often defined as the Average Number of Ancestors (ANA) which measures “the average number of abstract elements (e.g., classes, components, or interfaces) inherited by each element of architecture model element” [7, 8]. It is computed based on the number of abstract elements, from a root element to all the other model elements in the hierarchy. In AIDOaRt, we computed this quality attribute at each phase of the project as follows:

- For the initial version of the architecture, we considered the average number of components implemented per interface. This was simply 1 since each functional interface was a refinement of precisely one component. We also considered the average number of components implemented by each solution. We obtained 2.38 with a median of 2 as a result. We believe that this reflects a reasonable alignment of the solutions with the various architectural components proposed by the core team.
- For the final version of the architecture, where detailed functional interfaces have been introduced as a refinement of the components and then mapped to the solutions accordingly, we obtained slightly higher abstraction indicators. 4.96 interfaces were implemented per solution, with a median of 3, thus achieving a total of 7.3 interfaces and components implemented on average per solution. We think that the granular level of detail needed by the project partners (to better map their solutions and use cases to the proposed architecture) justifies this increase. Anyway, it remains reasonably low and avoids threatening the overall maintainability of the architecture.

The work in [19] defines abstraction as “the ratio of abstract classes in a component to the total number of classes.” In our case, we get a ratio of 0.2, in the initial version of the architecture, for the number of components over the total number of components and interfaces. In the final version, we get a ratio of 0.38 when considering the number of concrete solutions over the total number of abstract elements, including components and interfaces.

We argue that these two low abstraction ratios reflect on the architectural design decisions that can be taken in the context of our methodology. Because of that, our methodology allows us to extend the resulting architecture while still preserving its global maintainability.

Decision Traceability aims at characterizing “to what extent architecture design decisions (ADD) are properly linked to requirements” [17]. Thus, higher values tend to indicate better decision traceability. Given that all our ADD in AIDOaRt are derived from our project requirements and objectives, we are tempted to assume a full decision traceability ratio of 1. However, the proportion of traceable ADD drops to 0.46 if we only consider the functional

interfaces proposed by our consortium members and strictly linked to specific partners' requirements.

In the end, our methodology allows to root the architecture design decisions in both the project's original requirements and the particular use cases and solutions requirements. As a consequence, we believe that this globally contributes to the clarity and maintainability of the resulting architecture.

Similarly, **Requirements Fulfillment** is defined as "the proportion of requirements in the specification associated with artifacts in the model" [17]. In AIDOaRt, the use case providers mapped each of their 187 use case requirements to one or more components and interfaces in the architecture. Based on that situation, we obtain a ratio of 1 reflecting the full mapping of the requirements to the corresponding artifacts in our architecture.

This highlights the high importance of the expressed requirements in the context of the proposed methodology. This also shows that our methodology allows us to (at least partially) fulfill all these requirements with the resulting architecture.

Decomposition is another interesting attribute that is used to evaluate the clarity and to facilitate the maintainability of architectures. It indicates "whether or not modules are decomposed into sub-modules such that at the lowest level a similar degree of decomposition is achieved across all modules" [2, 17]. In AIDOaRt, we measure how uniformly the components (resp. interfaces) are distributed over the various architecture layers (resp. components) by using the Gini coefficient [12, 20]. The coefficient value is a number in the range $[0, 1]$ where a low value denotes a more balanced distribution in the population, and a higher value means more inequality (i.e., a small part of the population has a significantly higher value than the rest). For our resulting architecture, the measured coefficients are 0.18 for the decomposition of layers into components and 0.3 for the decomposition of components into interfaces (cf. Figure 7). We also obtained a similar Gini coefficient of 0.24 for the decomposition when aggregating the number of interfaces per architecture layer.

These low coefficients reflect the quite balanced and well-distributed decomposition of the resulting architecture (in terms of main components, sub-components, and functional interfaces) that can be achieved thanks to the application of our methodology.

Understandability is defined as "the number of connections between components divided by $N^2 - N$, where N is the number of components" [21]. This metric is evaluated at 0.033 in our architecture if we consider the connections between the components, and 0.011 if we consider the connections between the components and interfaces.

These low values indicate that our methodology allows to obtain a resulting architecture that remains understandable and thus more easily usable. Interestingly, this was also directly perceived by the users of the methodology, i.e., our project partners (cf. Section 11).

It is important to mention that our methodology and resulting architectures may also meet other quality metrics that we did not include in the evaluation. This is notably due to difficulties in interpreting some definitions found in the literature or finding a relevant threshold for the measured value. For instance, a small **size** metric [18] can indicate in some cases a better maintainability, adaptability or portability of an architecture resulting from the application of our methodology. In the particular context of the

Figure 7: Gini Coefficients of 0.18 and 0.3 for layers decomposition into components (left) and components decomposition into interfaces (right). It is the area ratio between the distribution curve (i.e., Lorenz curve) and the line of equal distribution (i.e., the straight line) to the entire area under the line of equal distribution.

AIDOaRt project, our methodology allowed us to obtain a reasonable size (~ 80 UML model elements). Nevertheless, there are many different definitions and measures for such a metric, and there is no clear acceptable range for the measured value (i.e., how small should the size be for the architecture to be considered portable or maintainable?). Due to such a limitation, we complemented our metrics-based evaluation with a survey that aimed to address the process and tooling associated to the methodology, in addition to the resulting architecture we obtained in the context of AIDOaRt.

9 Empirical Evaluation: Survey Instrument

To assess the perceived quality, usefulness, and value of the proposed methodology (including the underlying process and the provided tooling) and of the resulting architecture, a dedicated survey [3] was carried out among the AIDOaRt partners. The study ran from the beginning of 2024 toward the end of the project. The respondents have actively used the shared architecture model throughout the complete project's lifetime. They participated in various refinements of the architecture design in order to prepare its final version. They also provided extensive mappings of their use case requirements and solutions descriptions to the architecture elements. To mitigate subjectivity bias, we deliberately excluded ourselves as responsible for the architecture design process in AIDOaRt (even though we were among the main beneficiaries of the proposed methodology).

In the survey composed of 8 different questions, we considered a Likert-like scale [13] from 1 to 5 for the respondents to indicate their level of agreement. We started by a first set of questions mostly related to the resulting architecture:

- Q1: *Is the AIDOaRt architecture clear and understandable? (e.g., all components are well described).*
- Q2: *Is the AIDOaRt architecture easy to use and explore? (e.g., easy to relate your UC requirements or solutions to the architecture components).*
- Q3: *Do you believe the architecture can be easily extended or used outside the scope of the AIDOaRt project?*

- *Q4: Has the way we organized the architecture helped ensure quality in your solutions/use cases developed? (e.g., collecting requirements and KPI, and mapping requirements, solutions, and components).*
- *Q5: Did the mapping collected within the architecture help identify potential collaborations? (i.e., looking for solutions/requirements mapped to the same architecture components instead of an exhaustive search across the large set of solutions and requirements).*

Before asking the last three questions, we reminded respondents that “to design the AIDOaRt architecture, we followed an incremental methodology (inspired by DevOps), the specification of the requirements and the main components were first collected/defined and then iteratively refined following the development phase of the tools and use cases.”. Then, we continued with a second set of questions focusing on the proposed methodology itself:

- *Q6: Has the AIDOaRt iterative architecting process helped to provide quality in the implemented solutions/tools?*
- *Q7: Did formalizing/defining the requirements and capabilities/interfaces help define the scope of the solution?*
- *Q8: Was it helpful to have requirements mapping to achieve desired outcomes (e.g., KPIs)?*

To capture additional qualitative feedback that can be relevant for our quality evaluation, we added an open comment text field after each question. These text fields ask: “Please, provide any justifications about the previous answer, and any comments or suggestions.”.

Finally, we provided a last general and open question to collect additional feedback regarding any of the previously mentioned aspects (e.g., process, tooling, architecture):

- *Overall: Please, provide any justifications about the previous answers, and any comments or suggestions about the architecture..*

10 Empirical Evaluation: Background of the Survey Respondents

The survey was answered by 34 different individual respondents in total. This represents an average of 1 respondent per partner in the project, excluding us. It also occurred that some partners had 2 to 4 respondents when they were particularly involved in the project and its architecture definition. Although this amount of data cannot be considered statistically representative, we believe that the feedback received still provides relevant complementary insights.

The background of the survey respondents is summarized in the charts of Figure 8:

- The majority of the respondents are solution providers (82%) coming from academia or industry, whereas the use case providers are only 30% (cf. Figure 8a). This is consistent with the structure of the AIDOaRt consortium, with only 10 use case providers among 30+ partners.
- Collaborations with universities and research institutes (59%) are relatively balanced compared to collaborations with industry (41%) (cf. Figure 8b).
- The domains of expertise of the partners span over a large panel of application areas for Cyber-Physical Systems (cf.

Figure 8c). The three main domains mentioned are Automotive (25%), Manufacturing (15%), and Maritime (10%), representing 50% of the respondents. Another quarter of the respondents work in domains such as Digital Life, Construction, Railway, or Cross-CPS domains. The last quarter covers several other more specific application domains such as telecommunication and networking, banking, insurance and finance, retail, renewable energies, and healthcare.

- We also collected the level of experience of our respondents in the three key research areas in AIDOaRt, namely MDE, DevOps, and AI (cf. Figure 8d). Most partners have at least 1-3 or 3-5 years of experience in these domains (47 – 70%), and some have 5-10 or 10-15 years of experience (18 – 30%). In contrast, only a few have 15+ years or no experience (3 – 12%). It is also important to note that each respondent indicated several years of experience in at least one of the three domains considered.

11 Empirical Evaluation: Detailed Qualitative Feedback

The open questions of the survey allowed us to collect more feedback from the respondents on the perceived quality and value of the proposed methodology and resulting architecture. Not all respondents provided such a feedback, and we voluntarily omitted all irrelevant comments such as “No comment” or “I was not involved in this; I got in later than the rest of my team”. In the end, we carefully studied all the exploitable comments and classified them as follows:

- **Positive:** The comment confirms our question statement, providing more details, an example, or a particular case relevant for the partner.
- **Negative:** The comment refutes or contradicts our question statement, often with arguments and explanations of the provided opinion.
- **Neutral:** The comment does not confirm or refute our question statement but completes it with an additional piece of information, remark, or advice.

For each question, we summarize the number of positive, negative, and neutral statements, as shown in the bar chart of Figure 9. We also plot the number of comments (cf. the “# Comments” line plot) collected for each question.

First of all, a comment may include several statements (positive, negative or neutral). This explains why, for some questions, the total number of statements is higher than the number of received comments. For example, *Q7* received 8 comments in which we identified a total of 17 statements: 7 positive, 3 negative and 6 neutral. We also notice that *Q1*, *Q5*, *Q7* and *Q8* received the highest number of comments, while *Q1*, *Q4* and *Q7* received the highest positive feedback. These questions relate to the clarity and understandability of the architecture and to the relevance of the proposed formalization process for requirements. They also reflect on the main role of the methodology in ensuring the quality of the solutions, identifying potential collaborations, defining the scope of these solutions, and achieving the desired outcomes of the project. *Q2* and *Q3* received fewer but equally positive comments compared to *Q1*. This may be explained by the fact that respondents did not want

(a) Roles

(b) Partnerships

(c) Domains

(d) Experience

Figure 8: Background of the survey respondents.

Figure 9: Number of positive, negative, and neutral statements in the comments provided by the respondents on each survey question and overall.

to elaborate more on aspects such as the ease of use, explorability, and extensibility of the architecture. Finally, comments on Q2, Q3 and Q6 contained the least number of negative statements. We may infer that they do not contradict our previous analysis on the architecture’s ease of use, explorability, extensibility. We think it also

comforts the role of the proposed methodology to improve quality both in the resulting architecture and the implemented solutions.

In what follows, we present an excerpt of key positive, negative, and neutral feedback on each question. In addition, we further analyze their rationale and explain how we may overcome some of the limitations:

- Q1 - Two negative statements pointed out “some aspects that can lead to discrepancies or ambiguities” or criticized “the granularity” of the proposed architecture. We fully understand these concerns, and we believe it is always a challenging process to achieve a common understanding of all the architectural elements or a universal agreement on the right level of granularity. However, the first respondent also acknowledged that “those ambiguities can help adoption by third parties adding specific semantics,” which goes more in the direction of our claim in Q3.
- Q2 - One negative feedback pointed out that “the architecture and related documentation [...] can be subject to erosion

when changes come after the end of the project” while agreeing on its importance within the project. We also partially share this concern and hope that the proposed methodology and resulting architecture also serve future related projects. In fact, some steps of our methodology were initiated in previous projects (e.g. MegaM@Rt, VeriDevOps, DataBio, or REVaMP2 [15, 16]) and the full methodology is now being used in another large collaborative project named MATISSE [6]. A positive comment highlighted that the modeling tool “*Modelio helps in surfing the information.*”.

- Q3 - One respondent pointed out that, being “*extremely abstract which is very good for extensibility*”, the architecture might be “*a bit imprecise to adapt to concrete problems*”. Another respondent anticipates that “*an expansion could apply to a subset of the AIDOaRt solutions*” but “*it is improbable that an expansion would pertain to the entire AIDOaRt project*”. However, five other respondents were positive and confirmed that the architecture’s “*level of granularity allows it to be adapted to other environments outside of the project*”, “*for example, security issues*”, as stated by another respondent.
- Q4 - We received a high number of positive feedback confirming that the proposed methodology and resulting architecture helped to ensure quality in the development of solutions and use cases. However, four negative statements were provided. For one partner, our claim does not apply in their case. Another wondered whether a “*more conventional working way would not have been equally efficient*”. We think they meant using plain unstructured text documents instead of a model-based common architecture to collect requirements and describe use cases, solutions, and their interconnections. While the “conventional” way may be flexible and easy to use for small projects, we believe that in large projects such as AIDOaRt and now MATISSE (involving 30+ partners), more structured model-based methodologies such as ours are a better fit.
- Q5 - We received an equal number of neutral and confirmation statements. The neutral statements mainly refer to the fact that the architecture was not the only tool used in AIDOaRt to identify potential collaborations. Indeed, we also ran five hackathons during the project’s face-to-face plenary meetings. In practice, they were an extremely useful means of establishing collaborations. As such, they efficiently complemented our methodology and our practical evaluation of the resulting architecture. In the end, the negative feedback was limited to two statements based on personal experience: one remark about the side-effect of establishing a strict vocabulary with the architecture (which may lead to misunderstanding), and a suggestion to use additional mapping analysis tools to enhance the discovery of potential collaborations.
- Q6 - The survey respondents largely agreed in their comments on the role of the proposed methodology, process, and tooling in providing quality in the implemented solutions. However, one respondent sees that “*it has helped with reporting, but not the actual collaboration/development*”, while another “*would say yes, but only as their suitability*

for purpose (i.e., the requirements for them) is concerned, not that much their functional quality.” which, we also believe, is left to the solution provider to consider in-depth and fully guarantee. Another respondent pointed out that “*a direct impact on the [solutions] implementation [quality] can only be achieved with prescriptive models/artifacts that can be used directly in the implementation process (e.g., code generation)*”. Although we agree with this statement for architectures dedicated to a particular software or system solution, we believe it is hard to achieve when designing a common generic architecture representing the high-level functional specification of multiple solutions (57 in total in AIDOaRt).

- Q7 - Comments summarize the respondents’ opinion on the utility of the model-based definition of requirements and capabilities when defining the scope of the solutions in our methodology. Most of them agreed, stating that “*formalization always help*”, and that formalizing “*data [models] was [particularly] helpful*”. Others said that it helped “*only partially*”, at least to “*guide the initial steps*” in the project. Another respondent argued that “*since the architecture is defined from a very high abstraction level, [...] it is difficult to combine [...] with the more hands-on work on the software [...], e.g., to formalize concrete APIs and interfaces between components*”. In this sense, one suggested to “*revisit and refine requirements, capabilities, and interfaces throughout the project life cycle to ensure they remain relevant and achievable*”. In fact, thanks to our methodology, we were able to achieve this refinement effort during the second year of the project when specifying the final version of the architecture. However, we could not push this refinement effort further in the last year of the project, since it was not planned in the project timeline. This remains a relevant path to follow in ongoing and future collaborative research projects such as MATISSE.
- Q8 - This question asked about the usefulness of the requirement mapping to the architecture components and interfaces in achieving the targeted outcomes. Several confirmed this usefulness especially “*for reporting*” and “*from the project point of view*” which “*could streamline the [use case and solution development] process and make it more efficient*”. Some respondents reported that “[some] requirements are not [...] directly mapped to KPIs”, and that “*[some] KPIs have been changed over time due to the run-time constraints raised during the actual [solution and use case] development*”. In general, this confirmed the relevance of our methodology for providing traceability and impact links between solutions, use case requirements and corresponding KPIs, as well as project level KPIs and objectives. However, this requires partners to detail their requirements mapping to the architecture and to the KPIs and, more importantly, to keep them updated throughout the whole project.

As Overall feedback, we received interesting additional comments and remarks. Some partners stated that the architecture is “*is interpreted sometimes differently by partners and/or [project’s] reviewers*”. Indeed, in a large collaborative project (30+ partners) over

a 3+ years period, it is difficult to achieve a common consensus on all aspects of a proposed common architecture. Another respondent says that “*due to the heterogeneous nature of the use cases, a common architecture is quite difficult to achieve*”. In addition, most partners would assign different team members to work on the project implementation in various phases of the project. Our initial architecture specification and the accompanying tool support documentation were comprehensive enough to get all partners equally actively involved in the model creation and revisions. However, it is undeniable that people who join the project in late phases could feel overwhelmed by the existing knowledge base. As a result, it can be challenging to make them fully efficient. Nevertheless, we remain convinced that an architecture model that is well documented and supported, in terms of process and tooling by a dedicated methodology, is still easier to master and handle than plain text and/or unstructured data spread over multiple documents.

Other partners said that the architecture “*became increasingly complex due to the various needs that emerged [which] made it complicated to use outside the project because it was too specialized*”. Related to this point, another partner argued that this is due to “*the difficulties to provide the reasoning framework to the potential [external] users, i.e., the domain model of the tokens used in the AIDOaRt vocabulary*”. Indeed, “*the understanding of what it is a tool, a component or an interface here is easy to take by software engineers trained in model-driven engineering, but might be hard to get for managers or other stakeholders coming from mechanical or systems engineering backgrounds for example*”. We believe this can be overcome by providing a comprehensive dictionary for the terminology we consider in the context of both our methodology and the resulting architectures. In AIDOaRt, we provided such a dictionary through specific deliverables that presented the architecture specification. We already started to follow a similar process for our new MATISSE project. The same respondent confirms that our proposed “*AIDOaRt Architecture is mainly a meta-architecture, this means it is a way of organizing knowledge so that it can be cohesively understood by architects, practitioners, and even managers. Its value is in the ability to select components that can be useful for concrete design, development, or in general models processing environments*”. This perception is aligned with our aspirations in AIDOaRt, and the corresponding architectural design decisions we took during the project.

12 Summary

The material reported in this companion document complements the main paper by providing concrete evidence of the practical application of the proposed methodology in AIDOaRt, as well as the detailed material supporting its empirical evaluation. The examples show how requirements, use-case scenarios, tool capabilities, roadmaps, architectural components, and implementation pipelines were connected through explicit traceability links. They also illustrate how the iterative process supported the progressive consolidation of the AIDOaRt architecture and enabled reuse across use cases. Finally, the evaluation material details the quality framework and metrics used to assess the resulting architecture, together with the complete survey instrument, the background of its respondents, and the full analysis of the collected qualitative feedback.

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